

ANALYSIS OF THE COMPACTION CYCLE IN THE VACUUM INFUSION MOLDING PROCESS

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SUMMARY: The compaction behavior of dry reinforcements has been the subject of much previous research work. However the research was mainly carried out for the Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) process where the compaction pressure goes up to 1 MPa, and higher compaction rates are involved. In the vacuum infusion molding process, the available compaction pressure never exceeds 1 bar. Accordingly, the analytical compaction models derived for the resin transfer molding process will not reflect the actual behavior of the material. It is known that the process is cost effective for the production of large structures. Normally for these structures, the infusion time is relatively long, which may affect the compressive response of the reinforcement. In their quest for reducing the infusion time, manufacturers have developed high permeable layers, which also affect the compressive response of the whole stack.

KEYWORDS: Wet / dry compaction, reinforcement relaxation, high permeable layer, vacuum infusion molding process, resin transfer molding process.

INTRODUCTION

The competitiveness of low cost manufacturing processes for Fiber Reinforced Composites (FRC), i.e., hand lay-up and spray-up technologies is threatened by increased environmental regulation that limits worker exposure to volatile organic compound (VOC). A recent survey of the industry [1] shows that open mold processes, i.e., hand lay-up and spray-up are extensively used, this is especially true for developing countries. These two techniques make extensive use of unsaturated polyester (UP), which typically contains between 30% and 45% of styrene as a reactive solvent. New legislation dealing with VOC emissions has identified the latter as the main harmful substance to eliminate. Accordingly, users of these techniques are required to seek new manufacturing methods to comply with the new legislation and protect their market's shares.

Among the existing alternatives, closed mould processes such as RTM attract considerable interest. However for large structures, the RTM technology is not cost effective since it involves high equipment costs, especially for building complex and heavy moulds, which can withstand the injection pressure. For manufacturing situations involving low production volumes of large structures, injection strategies have been developed that use the vacuum pressure as the only driving force to achieve the impregnation of the reinforcement inside the

mould cavity. As mentioned by Williams et al.[2], early interest for these techniques goes back to the 1940's when the so-called Marco method was introduced. Over the past years, many developments have helped the vacuum infusion processes to become economically viable; and various methods are available on the market today. Among them, one can mention the SCRIMP method, the Quick Draw VARTM method, the Resin Injection Recirculation Method (RIRM) and the Prestovac Method. Actually, these methods are derivatives of the original Marco method; therefore they share many common features. Trial and error was the adopted strategy to obtain the correct results and no rigorous scientific approach was followed during all the development steps.

In vacuum infusion, one is mainly concerned with large structures that involve large amounts of materials and often require long processing times. The completion of the impregnation of the preform before resin gelation remains a major challenge. Another concern is the prediction of the final thickness of the part, which is governed by the compaction behaviour of the material being used. Finally, surface finish and print-through are considered as areas where substantial improvements should be made to enable the introduction of the process in the aerospace industry. These concerns show that the process is not fully understood, and outlines the need for additional information on the effects of the various process parameters. Furthermore, the normal end users of the process are mainly small companies where the resources allocated to the development of complex simulation tools are limited. From this arises the need for affordable and simply formulated simulation models which may help the industrials to avoid production pitfalls. The performance of such simulation tools and models depends mainly on two factors:

- a thorough understanding of the different mechanisms governing the process, in order to handle correctly the input data
- a mathematical model used for representing the physical process.

Recently, a 1-D model has been proposed [3] for the process by taking into account the transverse equilibrium that holds inside the mold cavity. A fairly good agreement was found between the simulation results and the infusion experiments, even though the simulation was implemented using compaction and permeability data specific to the resin transfer molding process. One way to contribute to the existing modeling effort is by deriving the appropriate analytical models for the compaction phase. In order to achieve this a comprehensive analysis of the compaction cycle should be performed.

In this paper compaction experiments, using various combinations of reinforcements, were performed. From the manufacturing point of view, it is suggested that two parameters will affect the compressive response of the reinforcement. First the compaction speed, this is related to the size of the structure to be infused. As an example, for a medium size structure ($< 2 \text{ m}^2$) only few seconds are needed to evacuate the air from the mold cavity, then one can assume a relatively high compaction speed, i.e., 2 mm/min. The second parameter concerns the stacking sequence. In this process, it is recommended that a high permeable layer is used to reduce the infusion time. However the introduction of this layer will modify the compaction behavior of the whole stack. Accordingly, the contribution of these two parameters in the compaction cycle will be investigated using wet and dry reinforcements.

EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

Compaction tests were performed using different reinforcements. The reinforcements were used either alone or combined with flow enhancement layers. Table 1 summarizes the technical data for the reinforcements being used.

Table 1: Surface weight and geometric structures of the reinforcements being used.

Reinforcement	Surface weight (g/m ²)	Structure
Devold DB 400-E01	420 g/m ²	[+45°/-45°]
Devold L 900-E11	884 g/m ²	[0°/90°]
CSM	600 g/m ²	Randomly chopped strand mat
Multimat Synchoglass	1450 g/m ²	It is a sandwich like construction consisting of 3D-glass fiber knitting core with chopped stitched glass fiber mat on each side. The surface weight is respectively equal to 450 g/m ² for each side of the mat and 500 g/m ² for the core
Rovicore 600/B5/600	1450 g/m ²	A sandwich likes construction consisting of non-woven synthetic core with large diameter fibers with fiberglass on either side. Each side of the reinforcement has a surface weight of 600 g/m ² . B5 designates the surface weight of the core 250 g/m ² .

The compaction tests were carried out with an Instron universal testing machine. Each reinforcement was cut in pieces of 150 mm x 150 mm, then the samples were placed on a flat steel plate in the testing machine and compressed by a circular plate (\varnothing 120 mm). From the data collected, the fiber volume fraction can be plotted as a function of the compaction pressure. Two different machine head speeds were selected: 0.05 mm/min and 2 mm/min. These values were selected in order to reflect the effect of the component size. Actually, small and medium size components require less time to evacuate the air encapsulated in the mould cavity. Therefore 2 mm/min can be viewed as a representative average value for the compaction speed. For large structures, as the retrieval of the encapsulated air is much slower, a low Compaction speed is more representative of the process.

For the experiments presented in this paper, the maximum compaction pressure does not exceed 1 bar, which corresponds to the applied vacuum pressure. Once this pressure was reached, the position of the machine head was kept constant, and the evolution of the compaction pressure was recorded for ten minutes. This experimental procedure was also applied for the saturated (wet) compaction. In this case, each layer was fully saturated with resin (an unsaturated polyester resin S 910-4138 from NESTE Chemicals), and the whole stack was positioned on a thermoplastic polyester (Mylar) film. A sealant tape acting as a dam to prevent the resin from escaping from the steel plate surrounded the border of the Mylar film. Resin was subject only to the pressure applied by the plate. The results will be presented first for the unidirectional reinforcement (Devold L900), then for a combined multilayer preform, which consist of a structural reinforcement and a flow enhancement layer.

ANALYSIS OF THE COMPRESSIVE RESPONSE OF AN UNIDIRECTIONAL REINFORCEMENT

Experimental results for different lay-ups presented in Fig. 1, show that for low compaction pressures (1bar) and for the 2 mm/min case, it appears that neither the number of layers nor the stacking sequence has any significant influence on the compaction behavior. As mentioned earlier, when the applied pressure reaches 1 bar, the machine head is maintained at

the same position for ten minutes. As shown in Figure 2, a drop in the applied pressure is observed. Apparently, the fibers start to rearrange and less fibers are in contact with the steel plate. Pearce and Summerscales [4,5] who conducted compaction experiments simulating both RIFT and RTM processes also confirmed this decrease in the load applied. According to the authors, in order to achieve the targeted fiber volume fraction in RTM, one has to apply successive loading cycles when closing the RTM mold. For vacuum infusion, applying this strategy is not straightforward. One possible alternative to reach the same results consists in applying the vacuum for the longer time possible before starting infusion. Besides, using this strategy can reduce the relaxation that takes place during infusion.

Fig.1 : Effect of the stacking sequence on the compressive response of Devold L900.

Following these observations, additional compaction experiments were limited to the 5-layer case. In the second series of tests, the effect of machine head speed on the compaction response of the reinforcement both in dry and wet conditions was investigated, the two stacking sequences, i.e. $[(0^\circ/90^\circ)_5]$ and $[(0^\circ)_5/(90^\circ)_5]$ were tested. After reaching 1 bar, the lay-up was subject to successive loading for approximately 10 min. The results presented in Fig.2, show that at lower compaction speed the resin is able to percolate out of the stack, which result in higher fiber content for the same vacuum pressure. As an example, for the saturated reinforcement compacted at a pressure of 0.8 bar and a machine head speed of 2mm/min, a fiber volume content of 54% was recorded compared to 57% for the one compacted at a machine head speed of 0.05 mm/min.

Fig.2 : Wet and dry compaction for different stacking sequences and machine head speed (L900-E11).

COMPRESSIVE RESPONSE OF A MULTILAYER PREFORM

Flow enhancement layers are a relatively recent development, aimed at improving the impregnation properties of aligned fiber reinforcements particularly at high volume fractions. Commercially available flow enhancement fabrics are said to offer a number of advantages over other aligned fabrics, in particular reduced infusion times which make possible the production of relatively large parts at high fiber volume fractions. The main disadvantage of these materials is the potential reduction in mechanical properties, compared to using a homogeneous reinforcement stack, caused by less uniformity in the fiber distribution.

For the vacuum infusion molding process, the use of flow enhancement layers is critical since it helps complete the infusion within a reasonable time. Actually, an experimental proof [3] was obtained for the substantial savings in infusion times when using these media. However one has to distinguish between a disposable format such as the one patented in SCRIMP process and a format aimed to be integrated into the part. The second format seems to be the obvious choice as it helps reducing the cost of consumable parts. However as outlined earlier, a substantial reduction in the mechanical properties is the major drawback of using this approach.

In all the compaction experiments, the flow enhancement layer was squeezed between five layers of the reinforcement (Devold DB-400). When analyzing the compaction behavior as shown in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively, the two flow enhancement layer exhibit a totally different behavior. For instance, in the case of Synchoglass, and despite its relatively larger surface weight, it was possible for the resin to percolate out from the multilayer stack, thus giving a thinner laminate than a similar stack with Rovicore as a flow enhancement layer. As an example, for a vacuum pressure of 0.8 bar, the final thickness of the laminate was around 6 mm with Synchoglass and 7 mm for the laminate with the Rovicore. This difference in thickness explains the shorter infusion time obtained with the Rovicore [3].

Fig.3: wet and dry compaction for DB400 with Synchoglass as flow enhancement layer.

Fig.4 : Wet and dry compaction for DB-400 with Rovicore as flow enhancement layer.

According to Fig.4 the compressive response of Devold is totally affected by the insertion of the flow enhancement layer. For instance the non-linear behavior observed in the compressive response of Devold decreases dramatically when the flow enhancement layer is squeezed in between. The initial thickness of the multilayer preform was around 9 mm and the flow enhancement layer accounts for almost 50% of the total thickness. This contribution to the total thickness will be even higher in application that requires the use of such layer.

Fig.5 : Wet and dry compaction for DB-400 with CSM as flow enhancement layer.

Using CSM as flow enhancement layer will not affect considerably the compressive response of the multilayer preform as shown in Fig.5. The non-linear behavior observed in the compressive response of Devold is still persistent, although the compressive response of the dry multilayer preform show some linearity due mainly to the rigidity of the flow enhancement layer. Actually, this rigidity is acquired by the flow enhancement layer when applying some binder for preforming operations. In wet conditions, the binder dissolves rapidly. Thus, for dry compaction, one can conclude that the compressive response is totally governed by the flow enhancement layer.

In Fig.6, the overall performance of the three flow enhancement layers combined with a stack of DB-400 is compared. It is clear that for CSM and for the compressive response in wet conditions, the compressive behavior is similar to the compressive behavior of Devold alone. However this remark can not be extended to the two other flow enhancement layers. In one case (Synchoglass) the relatively larger surface weight and thickness ratio (Syncho/Devold) in addition to the 3D structure of the core will definitely affect the compressive response of the multilayer preform whether in wet or dry conditions. In the other case (Rovicore), it looks like the non-woven synthetic core is responsible for the linear behavior observed for the multilayer preform. Consequently further investigation is required for this material, especially its time-dependent properties.

Fig.6 : Assessment of the performance of the different flow enhancement layers.

CONCLUSION

The work presented in this paper is a first step toward the definition of compaction models for the vacuum infusion molding process. According to the results presented here, it is critical to select the proper compaction rate, which will affect the ultimate fiber content. Regarding the use of the flow enhancement layer, it is clear that the introduction of this layer will definitely affect the compressive response of the whole multilayer preform. Furthermore, since this layer affect the impregnation process, i.e., impregnation is no longer in-plane but takes place through the transverse direction. Then for thick laminates, one has to investigate whether the compressive response of the whole stack is affect by the positioning of this layer. In addition, it is required to develop a new experimental set-up to simulate the continuous flow of the resin during the impregnation phase.

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